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Fiscal Policies And Manufacturing Sector Performance In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the fiscal policies and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria, using data for the period of 1981-2023, the sub-objectives were to: Determine the effect of government spending on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria; Ascertain the influence of taxation on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria; Investigate the influence of interest rate on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. Ordinary Least Squared (OLS) method of data analysis was adopted because of its Best Linear Unbiased Estimators (BLUE) properties. The data for the variables used was sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The variables used were manufacturing sector output as the dependent variable, while government spending on manufacturing sector output, interest rate, taxation were the independent variables and money supply is the control variable. The study adopted the unit root test, co-integration approach, as well as Error Correction Mechanism to analyses the corrected data. E- View software were used for the analysis. The study found that Government spending has significant positive effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria, Taxation has significant negative effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria, Interest rate has no significant effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. The study recommends that Government expenditure should be channeled towards boosting our in fact manufacturing firms; Government spending should be more of capital than recurrent in order to keep generating returns (revenue) and enhancing manufacturing firms. Government in the short-run should reduce tax to our domestic infant manufacturing industries; this would enhance their productive capacity. Monetary authorities in Nigeria should reduce the interest rate on loans to the manufacturing-sub sector of the economy. This will increase the output of that sector

Keywords: fiscal policies, manufacturing sector performance, interest rate, taxation, money supply

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Fiscal policy is generally known as the use of spending, borrowing and tax as fiscal tools by the government to manage and control the economy. Fiscal policy as defined by Aiyedogbon et al. (2023) is a key stabilization tool used to undertake measures that controls and regulates the amount, volume, availability, and also how money is channeled within an economy, to achieve the set macroeconomic targets and to constrict the undesired in the economy. Macroeconomic stabilization is a policy that can be used to regulate or modify the economy through fiscal and monetary policies. The roles of fiscal policy to the development of manufacturing sector have been an area of growing concerned in the emerging countries. Fiscal policy is used to achieve macroeconomic stability and is a policy that promotes economic growth and stabilization. Fiscal policy is the use of government revenue collection (taxation) and expenditure (government spending) to control the economy (Eze, 2013).

The two main instruments of fiscal policy are: government taxation and government expenditure. It can also be seen as government spending policies that influence macroeconomic conditions. These policies

affect tax rates, interest rates and government spending, in an effort to control the economy (Eze and Ogiji, 2013). Fiscal policy is the means by which a government adjusts its level of spending, taxes and borrowed fund domestic and external (public debt) in order to review and influence a nation's economy. It is used along with the monetary policy which the Central Bank uses to influence money supply in a nation. In other words, fiscal policy is a major economic stabilization tool that involves measure taken to regulate and control the volume, cost and availability as well as direction of money in an economy to achieve some specified macroeconomic policy objective and to take away undesirable trends in the economy.

Adams (2022) opined that before the great Britain's unemployment crises of 1920's and the great depression of the 1930's, it was generally held that the appropriate fiscal policy for the government was to maintain a balance budget. Fiscal policy of Nigeria aims to stimulate economic growth, reduce poverty, enhance the growth rate of Gross Domestic product (GDP), decrease inflation, improve the balance of payment accumulate saving and reserves, improve the exchange rate of Nigeria naira Okorie (2017). Fiscal policy is used by a government to control the economy toward a desired objective. Tax is the major fiscal tool used in Nigeria to attain the set macroeconomic targets, control the activities of the financial sector and ascertain the needed investment for growth and development. This tax system greatly affects the development of manufacturing sector, in the case of Nigeria, tax is a source of revenue to the government, hence the tax rate is increased to acquire as much revenue possible by all means (Alugbuo et al., 2023).

Increase in companies' tax makes it difficult for industries to raise sufficient fund as capital in the capital market, also internal source of fund is taxed. Hence, companies resort to borrowing which sometimes if too much hinders the business ability to create investments. The implementation of fiscal policy is essentially routed through government's budget. The role of fiscal policy on the output and capacity utilization of the industry sector cannot be overemphasized. Fiscal policy drives the market for the manufacturing sector through the purposeful manipulation of government revenue and expenditure. Fiscal policy also provides the legal, social and economic framework required for a profitable operation (Pettinger, 2017).

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate the effect of fiscal policies on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the proposed study are to;

1. Determine the effect of government spending on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the influence of taxation on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria
3. Investigate the influence of interest rate on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria

1.3 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the proposed study:

Ho₁: Government spending has no significant effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria

Ho₂: Taxation has no significant effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria

Ho₃: Interest rate has no significant influence on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Fiscal Policy

This is the use of the instruments of tax and government expenditure to control the activities that occur in an economy. The main target is to foster enhanced growth and drastically reduce poverty levels in the country. It is referred to as the government budget policy for controlling the tax and expenditure levels within the economy. It is deliberate action of the government to achieve macroeconomic objectives of the nation (Muhamad & Henry, 2020). Ighoroje and Akpokerere (2021) expatiated that fiscal policy comprises the use of taxation, government spending and public debt to affect the rate and growth of aggregate demand, creation of job opportunities and output. Hence, the policy involves all the means through which government generate revenues, incur expenses and make repayments in the quest to

regulate the economy. Fiscal policy has four major components which are; taxation, expenditure, investment & disinvestment and debt/ surplus management.

Gbanador (2017) defines fiscal policy as a deliberate action undertaken by the government to achieve its economic objectives using the fiscal instruments of taxation, government spending and the budget deficit. Fiscal policy encompasses the strategic employment of government funds, including taxation and borrowings, to navigate economic activities and shape the levels of demand, output, and employment growth within an economy. It involves the macroeconomic management conducted by the government, leveraging its revenue and expenditure capacities to actualize specific economic goals, such as fostering economic growth and development, as highlighted by Medee and Nembee (2011). Fiscal policy refers to that part of government policy concerning the raising of revenue through taxation and other sources and deciding on the level and pattern of expenditure for the purpose of influencing economic activities. It is a policy under which the government uses its expenditure and revenue programmes to produce desirable effects and avoid undesirable effects on national income, production and employment.

2.1.2 Manufacturing Sector

Manufacturing is the intricate process that involves the utilization of tools, human labour, machinery, and chemical processes to transform raw resources into final consumer goods, intermediates, or semi-finished products, as highlighted by Ogundipe (2022). This multifaceted sector also incorporates the utilization of cutting-edge technology, sophisticated equipment, and machinery to produce goods and services that enhance human welfare and elevate people's quality of life, as emphasized by Okon (2017).

It stands as a cornerstone for economic prosperity, playing fundamental role in the production of goods and services, the creation of job opportunities, and the generation of substantial income. The manufacturing sector, acting as a driver for economic advancement, propels structural transformation and economic diversification, allowing a nation to capitalize on its resource wealth and diminish dependence on foreign aid, as articulated by Egbiku Joshua (2018). According to Ogundipe (2022), manufacturing is a detailed process involving tools utilization, machinery, human labour and chemical processes to convert raw materials into finished goods, intermediate goods or semi-finished goods. This sector is a complex one that also contains the utilization of advanced technology, complex equipment and machinery to manufacture goods and services that improve human welfare and quality of life (Abiola, 2024).

Productivity plays a major role in the economic prosperity of a nation, generation of huge income and creation of jobs. Manufacturing sector plays a very vital role in determining the extent to which any nation is developed especially in the case of underdeveloped and developing countries. Solow (1956), highlights some causes of growth in a nation which are diminishing marginal productivity of capital, exogenous technological progress, rate of substitution of capital for labor and vice versa, constant returns to scale. These factors together with savings and investment contribute highly to the immediate growth in any economy.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Musgrave Theory of Public Expenditure

Musgrave (1959) proposed a development model that demonstrates how a link between the pattern of economic growth and the rise in public spending may exist. The theory contend that government expenditure is what drives economic growth and explains how the economy shifts from a traditional economy to one that is industrialized. He observes that high levels of per capita income, typical of developed economies, the rate of public sector growth tends to fall as the more basic wants are being satisfied. In tracing the work of Rostow and Musgrave, where they put forward development model as the cause for growth in public expenditure, the theory, therefore, presents public expenditure as a prerequisite for economic development. The theory stressed that as economic growth takes place, the balance of public investment shifts towards human capital and infrastructural development.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ogunjobi, Oluga, Oyeniyi and Oladipo, (2025) examined the impact of the labour market and the manufacturing sector on Nigeria's economic growth from 1993 to 2023. Employing the Solow-Swan growth model and Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) analysis, the study investigates the relationship between economic growth and key variables such as labour market participation,

manufacturing output, gross fixed capital formation, inflation, and interest rates. The findings reveal that the labour market, manufacturing output, and gross fixed capital formation positively and significantly influence Nigeria's real GDP, indicating their pivotal roles in driving economic growth. Conversely, inflation and interest rates exhibit a negative but significant effect on economic growth. The study highlights the need for targeted policies to enhance workforce skills, increase credit accessibility for small and medium-sized enterprises, and foster public-private sector collaborations to boost manufacturing and economic growth. These insights provide valuable recommendations for policymakers aiming to achieve sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Edeh and Okia (2024) examined the impact of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria for the period (1981-2021). The main objective of the study was to examine the impact of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. For this study, annual time series data on manufacturing sector output, government expenditure, taxation, trade openness, inflation rate, exchange rate and government borrowing were collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) 2021 Annual Statistical Bulletin. To analyse the data, the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression technique was used. The results showed that government expenditure has positive and significant impact on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. There is a uni-directional causality flowing from manufacturing sector output to government expenditure between government expenditure and manufacturing sector output in Nigeria, which means that past values of government expenditure cannot be used to predict the future values of manufacturing sector output product. In addition, past values of manufacturing sector output product can be used to predict the future values of government expenditure. Based on the findings, it is recommended that government should enhance its revenue base by diversifying its revenue sources, this can be done by increasing the amount of money invested in other sectors of the economy by 30 percent such as agricultural sector, tourism, etc, this can provide sufficient revenue to run government activities and enhance manufacturing performance in the long-run.

Ubong, Id and Ekpe, (2024) examined the influence of fiscal policy (government expenditure and taxation) and interest rate on the manufacturing sector of the Nigerian economy was explored for the period 1981 to 2021. The study utilized the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model approach since some of our variables were integrated at level and others at first difference, and the bounds test reporting the existence of long run relationship in the model. Findings of the study in indicated that in the short run, government expenditure and its one-period lag exerted a negative and significant influence on manufacturing sector performance; value added tax exerted a positive and significant effect on manufacturing sector performance while its one-period lag exerted a negative and significant effect; and interest rate exerted a positive and significant effect on manufacturing sector performance. In the long run, government expenditure put forth a negative but insignificant effect on manufacturing sector performance; while value added tax and interest rate exert positive and significant effect. In the disaggregated model, recurrent expenditure exerts a negative and significant effect; capital expenditure exerted a positive and significant effect; value added tax exerted a negative and significant effect; and interest rate put forth a positive and significant influence on manufacturing sector performance. The study recommended that there is need for a reduction in the cost of governance as a huge proportion of public spending is used in running the government other than being utilized in stirring critical sectors that could stir manufacturing sector performance.

Olawale, (2024) delved into the correlation between Nigeria's manufacturing sector and Government Capital Expenditure. Employing regression analysis, we leverage time series data spanning 1981 to 2022 to shed light on this dynamic relationship. The study arms the stationarity of all variables after first differencing. Furthermore, the Johansen co-integration test unveils a long-run equilibrium relationship among the selected variables, namely Value of Manufacturing output, Government Capital Expenditure, Value Added Tax, and Customs and Excise Duty. The analysis uncovers a robust and positive connection between the growth performance of the manufacturing sector and Government Capital Expenditure throughout the examined timeframe. The findings indicate that increased Government Capital Expenditure correlates with enhanced growth in the manufacturing sector output. This study underscores the critical role of public investment in fostering economic growth and industrial development. The

results suggest that strategic allocation of resources towards infrastructure, regulatory frameworks, and supportive policies can significantly impact the vibrancy and competitiveness of Nigeria's manufacturing sector.

Iningba and Chukwunyere (2024) examined the impact of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria from 1985-2022. The study used government expenditure on manufacturing sector using grants from bank of industry (BOI), government tax revenue on manufacturing sector as indicators of fiscal policy while manufacturing sector performance was measured by manufacturing sector share of output. The research utilized time series data obtained from the central bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin, the world development indicators (WDI) of the world bank and Bank of industry (BOI). The data analysis method utilized ADF unit root testing, ARDL bound co-integration. The outcome of ADF unit root testing indicated the presence of a combination of integrated of order zero (O), integrated of order one (1). The ARDL bound co-integration revealed the presence of a long-term link among manufacturing sector output, grants from bank of industry, as government expenditure and government tax revenue. All these contribute slowly in Nigeria.

Emily (2024) examined the impact of fiscal policy indicators on the non-manufacturing industrial sector in Nigeria in periods 1987 to 2022. Secondary data was sourced from CBN statistical bulletin, and the study adopted the auto-regressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique for its analysis. The result of the findings revealed that government recurrent expenditure and oil taxation have a significant positive effect on non-manufacturing industrial sector in Nigeria, but non-oil taxation has a positive effect on manufacturing industrial output, which still remained insignificant in boosting industrial output. Government capital expenditure, public external and domestic debts negatively affected manufacturing industrial sector in Nigeria.

Aiyedogbon, Olorunfemi and Obumneke, (2023) investigated the effect of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria between 1986 and 2021. The type of data utilized was secondary and was extracted from the Central Bank of Nigeria's 2021 statistical records. The Fully modified ordinary Least Square method of analysis was adapted in carrying out the analysis. Unit root tests were carried out on each of the variables used in the study to avoid spurious regression results, and the results confirmed variables are all stationary at first difference. The Co-integration ARDL bound test showed that long-run relationship exists between the variables, and the conditions necessary to apply the Fully Modified ordinary Least Square method (FMOLS) met. The study's insights demonstrated that fiscal policy strategies significantly bolster the outputs of the manufacturing Sector output. The article advises that the budget and national planning should earmark increased resources for foundational advancements in their fiscal plans, such as electricity and transportation, as this will augment manufacturing industry results. Additionally, tax breaks and incentives should be granted to the manufacturing sector of Nigeria economy.

Alugbuo et al. (2023) examined fiscal policy, automatic stabilizers and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria between 1981 and 2022. Secondary data sourced from World Development Indicators (WDI) was used, and ARDL method of estimation was applied. Findings revealed that aggregate government spending is inversely related to manufacturing sector output in the short-run, and in the long-run, it is said to be positively related. Revenue generated from tax also had an inverse relationship with manufacturing sector output in the examined period, which contributed immensely to manufacturing sector performance in past periods. Gross capital formation had an insignificant positive nexus with manufacturing sector output in the examined period.

RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Theoretical Framework

This growth model was developed by John Maynard Keynes (1936) in his book "The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money". The Keynesian growth model establishes the rationale for government intervention in the economy to enable stability and stimulation, especially during periods of downturn. For instance, during the Great Depression (1929 – 1939), this model provided a way out in the United States. Aggregate demand is the drive of growth in this model, and it comprises of consumption,

government spending, investment, imports and exports. As aggregate demand increases, business activities tend to respond positively which then brings about increase in employment and income, the later leads to increase in consumption further increasing demand. The role of government during periods of downturn is to make use of the fiscal tools by reducing tax or increasing government expenditure, and vice versa during periods of boom to revive the economy. Increase in government expenditure must be backed by corresponding economic activities, for it to deliver the expected result and not cause more problems like inflation. Through this, aggregate demand is boosted and growth increases. Also, government spending has a multiplier effect, that is., the initial increase in government spending can produce a greater overall increase in economic output. This effect necessitates the need for government spending to boost economic activities even in periods that private sectors suffer insufficiency; this will continue to promote growth. Public expenditure increases money supply in the economy, creating avenue for more investment, and investments facilitate the development process of a nation as well as industrialization (Emily, 2024). This model also includes other factors that influence economic growth and development such as improvements in productivity, technological progress, labor force inclusion rates, etc.

3.2 Model Specification

This research shall employ econometric method according to modalla (1992) this method gives the best techniques for the verification and reputation of theories it also provides quantitative estimation of the relationship among variables without much subjective judgment. The specification of econometrics model is always based on econometrics theory or any available information relating to the phenomenon being studied (koustsoyiannis 1997), hence the specification of the model adopted for this investigation is implicitly stated as follows

$$MSO = F(GSP, TAX, INT, MS).$$

Where

MSO	-	Manufacturing Sector Output
GSP	-	Government Spending
TAX	-	Taxation
INT	-	Interest Rate
MS	-	Money Supply (Control Variable)
F	-	Functional notation

The above equation can be put in an econometric form as;

$$MSO = b_0 + b_1 GSP + b_2 TAX + b_3 INT + b_4 MS + U$$

Where

B0	=	Autonomous or intercept
B1	=	Coefficient of parameter GSP
B2	=	Coefficient of parameter TAX
B3	=	Coefficient of parameter INT
B4	=	Coefficient of parameter MS
U	=	Stochastic variable or error term

Our model can be also be stated in a logged form as

$$\text{LogMSO} = C + B_1 \text{LogGSP} + \text{LOG} B_2 \text{TAX} + B_3 \text{INT} + B_4 \text{MS} + \mu$$

3.3 Justification of the Model

The research work used the ordinary least square (OLS) because of the following:

3. OLS are expressed in terms of the observable, that is sample quantities (that is x and y). Therefore they can be computed
 - ii. They are point estimates that are given in the sample; each estimator will provide only a single (point) value of the relevant population parameter.
 - iii. Once the OLS estimators are obtained from the sample data, the sample regression line can easily be obtained

3.4 Nature and Sources of Data

The study utilize annual secondary time series data spanning from 1981 to 2023. The choice of data period coverage is based on availability of data. With a total of 43 observations, the estimation will have adequate degree of freedom (df) that improves statistical inferences. Thus, estimates based on this data coverage not only ensure consistency of results but also guarantee robustness of results to different diagnostics tests. These secondary sources of data for this study were sought through several editions of CBN statistical bulletin.

s/n	Variables	Sources
1	Manufacturing Sector Output (MSO):	CBN statistical bulletin
2	Government Spending (GSP):	CBN statistical bulletin
3	Taxation (TAX)	CBN statistical bulletin
4	Interest Rate (INT)	CBN statistical bulletin
5	Money Supply	CBN statistical bulletin

RESULT PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.0 Introductions

This chapter presents the empirical results and discussion of findings. Ordinary Least Square was used as technique for the analysis; the result was subject to different statistical and econometrics test. We begin by discussing the order of integration of the variables.

4.1 Presentation and Analysis of Data

4.1.1 Unit Root Test

The first stage of co-integration and error correction model is to test for unit root, the whole analysis then proceed from it. There exists unit root in most macroeconomics time series. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze whether the series are stationary or not whenever time series data are involved. The presence of unit root implies that the time series under investigation is non-stationary, the absence of a unit roots shows that stochastic process is stationary. The augmented dickey-fuller (ADF) test would be employed in this test

Tables 4.1 Unit Root Result

Variable	ADF	Integration	Significance
LMSO	-5.584420	I (1)	1%
LGSP	-4.103512	I (2)	1%
LTAX	-6.250675	I (1)	1%
INT	-5.169842	I (1)	1%
MS	-4.662953	I (1)	1%

Source: Author's computation using e-view version 11

Following the result of ADF test above it is observed that none of the variables are stationary at level, but the entire variables become stationary at 1st difference, except government spending who became stationary at 2nd differences. This also follows the simple rule of thumb that once a unit root is conform, co-integration is necessary to established.

4.1.2 Co-integration Analysis

The aim of co-integration analysis is to determine the long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables. In the Engle-granger co integration analysis, variables of consideration are said to be co integrated or have a long-run equilibrium relationship if in the OLS regression of one variable on the others. Co-integration exists among the variables if they are integrated of the same order. The implication of this analysis is that deviation or drift may occur between the variables but this is temporary as equilibrium hold in the long run for them. In this study we used the Johansen co-integration approach to examine the existence of long-run relationship between the variables of interest. Below is the summary of co integration result

Table 4.2 co-integration result test

Unrestricted Co-integration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace static	0.05 critical value	Prob**
None *	0.744863	89.14478	40.17493	0.0000
At most 1*	0.364812	34.50652	24.27596	0.0018
At most 2*	0.333849	16.35316	12.32090	0.0100
At most 3	0.002587	0.103599	4.129906	0.7912
At most 4	0.019806	10.680150	4.129906	0.4691

Source: Author's computation using e-view version 11

Trace test indicates 3 co-integrating equ(s) as the 0.05 level* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level ** mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) P – values.

Unrestricted co-integration Rank Test (Maximum Eigen value)

Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace static	0.05 critical value	Prob
None *	0.744863	54.63826	24.15921	0.0000
At most 1*	0.364812	18.15337	17.79730	0.0442
At most 2*	0.333849	16.24956	11.22480	0.0061
At most 3	0.002587	0.103599	4.129906	0.7912
At most 4	0.333855	10.019806	0.680150	4.129906

Source: Author's computation using e-view version 8.1

Max-Eigen value test indicates 3 co-integrating equations at the 0.5 level* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level **mackinnon-Haug-michelis (1999) P-values.

Trace test value and Max-Eigen indicates 3 co-integrating equations at the 0.05 level. This suggests a long run equilibrium relationship among the variables.

Co-integration is a pre-requisite for error correction mechanism following the result of co-integration, there is a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variable, hence, we can move over to error correction mechanism.

4.2 PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULT

Table 4.3 Error Correction Model Result

Dependent Variable: LMSO

Method: Least Squares

Date: 05/02/25 Time: 13:51

Sample (adjusted): 1982 2023

Included observations: 42 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.066247	0.200938	3.516637	0.0000
LGSP	0.536093	0.054200	9.890924	0.0000
LTAX	-0.359694	0.056871	-6.324678	0.0000
INT	-0.002929	0.009303	-0.314809	0.7547
LMS	0.807644	0.046312	3.743903	0.0000
ECM(-1)	-0.715581	0.130533	-5.481974	0.0000
R-squared	0.620500	Mean dependent var		7.870515
Adjusted R-squared	0.611905	S.D. dependent var		0.626620
S.E. of regression	0.185985	Akaike info criterion		-0.414953
Sum squared resid	1.279852	Schwarz criterion		-0.208088
Log likelihood	13.71401	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-0.339129
F-statistic	107.1022	Durbin-Watson stat		1.885042
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Author's computation using e-view version 11

Interpretation of the Regression Result

Coefficient of determination

The R^2 of the regression coefficient or the measure of goodness of fit is used to judge the explanatory power of the linear or multiple regressions. It shows the percentage change in the dependent variables. When the $R^2 = 1$, indicates a 100% explanation of the dependent by the independent variables. The worst being $R^2 = 0$, so the closer R^2 is to 1 the better the fitness of the model. From our regression result in table 4.2 above our R^2 is 62% and being the test of goodness of fit, this means that our independent variables explained about 62% of the total variation in the dependent variable, leaving the remaining 38%. This would be accounted for by other variables outside the model, as captured by the error term.

The adjusted R^2 is 61%, meaning that even with adjustment in the independent variables; they can still explain about 61% of the change in the dependent variables.

F- Statistic

F- Statistic which is used for joint influence of the explanatory variables on the dependent variables, it tests for the statistical significance of the entire regression plane. From the regression result in table above, the value of our f- statistics in the computed output is 107.1022, while its probability value is 0.000000 as a result we accept and state that there is a significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

T- Statistics

T- Statistics measures the individual statistics significance of the variables. The model shows that government spending is statistically significant to the manufacturing sector output in Nigeria given its values as -4.103512. Followed by taxation which is statistically significant, this implies that taxation has contributed to the manufacturing sector output. Interest rate is statistically insignificant. However money supply has positive and significant effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria.

Interpretation Based on Economic Criteria

Apriori criteria is determined by the existing economic theories and states the size and magnitude of our parameter estimates. The model shown that government spending has a positive sign given its value as 0.536093 this implies that increase in government spending increases the manufacturing sector output. However, taxation has a negative sign, given its value as -6.250675 this implies that a unit decrease in taxation will lead to an increase in manufacturing sector output. From the regression result, it was observed that interest rate has a negative sign given its value as -0.002929. This implies that decrease in interest rate will increase manufacturing sector output. It further suggests that all our variables confirm to apriori expectation.

Interpretation Based On Econometrics

The Durbin – Watson, test for auto correlation, will be used to test for the presence or otherwise of first order serial correlation. When the value of DW is closer or a little bit above 2.00, it implies the absence of auto correlation among the explanatory variable in the model. From our result in table 4.2 above, the value of DW is (1.8). This does satisfy the above stated condition and implies the absence of auto correlation. Hence our variables can be used for predictive purpose.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

The need to examine the collected data and stated hypothesis has called for this sector. The result will be composed with the statistical criteria to see if the preconceived notion in this research work holds or not.

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Government spending has no significant effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria

From the result report of our test in the table 4.3 above, we find out the value of our t-test for Government spending is 9.890924 with a probability of 0.0000, this probability value is less than the desired level of significance (0.05). We accept the alternative and reject the null hypothesis, which says Government spending has significant effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Taxation has no significant effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria

From the result report of our test in the table 4.3 above, we find out the value of our t-test for Taxation is -6.324678 with a probability of 0.0000, this probability value is less than the desired level of significance

(0.05). We accept the alternative and reject the null hypothesis which says, that Taxation has significant effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Interest rate has no significant influence on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria

From the result report of our test in the table 4.3 above, we find out the value of our t-test for Interest rate is -0.314809 with a probability of 0.7547, this probability value is less than the desired level of significance (0.05). We accept the alternative and reject the null hypothesis, which says Interest rate has significant influence on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of findings

This chapter is aimed at summing up the findings of this study as well as to draw the conclusion from the research work. Secondly the researcher gives recommendations based on the findings of the study. From the analysis of data presented, a number of findings were made from the study which examine the fiscal policies and manufacturing sector output in Nigeria and are as follows:

- i. Government spending has significant positive effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria
- ii. Taxation has significant negative effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria
- iii. Interest rate has no significant effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

The study focuses on the impact of fiscal policy on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Manufacturing sector is seen as an engine of growth in the developmental processes of the economy. The study adopts graph, co-integration and error correction model on a time series data from 1981 to 2023. The study regressed fiscal policy proxied by manufacturing sector output. The regression result reveals that about 62% of the systematic variation in the dependent variable is explained by the three independent variables such as Government Expenditure taxation and interest rate The F-statistic is significant at the 5% level showing that there is a linear relationship between the MOP and the three independent variables. The result revealed that government expenditure have positive and significant effect on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria, while taxation have negative and significant impact on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria, furthermore interest rate has negative and insignificant effect manufacturing sector output. based on the magnitude and the level of significance of the coefficient and p-value. The result also reveals that there is long-run relationship between fiscal policy and manufacturing sector output, as evidenced by the co-integration

The researcher concluded that the success of fiscal policy in promoting manufacturing sector depends on the level of public revenue available, the direction of public expenditure and its implementation.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. Government expenditure should be channeled towards boosting our in fact manufacturing firms, Government spending should be more of capital than recurrent in order to keep generating returns (revenue) and enhancing manufacturing firms.
- ii. Government in the short-run should reduce tax to our domestic infant manufacturing industries; this would enhance their productive capacity.
- iv. Monetary authorities in Nigeria should reduce the interest rate on loans to the manufacturing-sub sector of the economy. This will increase the output of that sector

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